

THE MAIN ASPECTS OF THE USE OF ICT TECHNOLOGIES BY A TEACHER

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Abstract. *This article states that primary school students, as noted in the state educational standard of primary general education, must independently organize the educational process. Therefore, today this category of children requires a special attitude in the learning process, since the growth of public knowledge in the framework of the study of information technology is realized quite quickly at the present stage of education. Studying the informational approach in the formation of media competence of younger students at the Russian language lessons at the general scientific level, teachers and scientists open up new opportunities for creating a coherent base for working with elementary school students using media tools in Russian language lessons, which will combine linguistics and media literacy.*

Keywords: *information technologies, methods of teaching computer literacy, information and communication technologies, formation, training, education.*

Effective use of the information and educational environment presupposes the competence of employees of an organization engaged in educational activities in solving professional tasks using ICT, as well as the availability of support services for the use of ICT. What is "ict competence" and why does a teacher need it?

As we have already read with you, the definition of what is fixed in the professional standard ICT competence of the teacher.

Let's pay attention to the difference between the term ICT competence and such terms as "Computer literacy", information culture, information and communication (ICT) competence and information literacy.

ICT competence, includes all of the above terms. So literacy in this area is the knowledge of what a personal computer is, software products, what their functions and capabilities are, this is the ability to "push the right buttons", knowledge of the existence of computer networks. ICT competence is already an effective application and use of information tools in pedagogical activity.

However, there are other interpretations of this term:

V.F. Burmakina: "ICT competence - confident possession of all the constituent skills ICT literacy for solving emerging issues in educational, educational and other activities"

A.A. Elizarov: "ICT competence is a set of knowledge, skills and experience of activity, therefore it is the presence of such experience that is decisive in relation to the performance of professional functions".

O.N. Shilov and M.B. Lebedev "ICT competence – this is the ability of an individual to solve educational, everyday, professional tasks using information and communication technologies";

L.N.Gorbunova and A.M. Semibratov: "ICT competence is the willingness and ability of a teacher to independently and responsibly use these technologies in their professional activities."

The professional standard indicates the following content of this competence:

general user ICT competence;

general pedagogical ICT competence (these are the general directions of using information technologies in the processes of education and upbringing);

subject-pedagogical ICT competence (reflecting the features of academic subjects (physics, mathematics, biology, literature, foreign language, history, etc.).

Let's consider the content of competence in more detail:

The General user component. The use of techniques and compliance with the rules for the beginning, suspension, continuation and completion of work with ICT tools, troubleshooting, provision of consumables, ergonomics, safety and other issues included in the results of mastering ICT in primary school.

Compliance with ethical and legal norms of the use of ICT (including the inadmissibility of unauthorized use and imposition of information).

Video audio recording of processes in the surrounding world and in the educational process.

Keyboard input. Audio-video-text communication (two-way communication

General pedagogical component Pedagogical activity in the information environment (IS) and its constant display in the IS in accordance with the tasks:

Planning and objective analysis of the educational process.

Transparency and clarity of the educational process to the outside world (and corresponding access restrictions).

Organization of the educational process: assignments for students, checking assignments before the next lesson, reviewing and fixing intermediate and final results, including in accordance with a given system of criteria, compiling and annotating student portfolios and their own, remote counseling of students when completing assignments, support for student interaction with the tutor.

The organization of the educational process in which students systematically in accordance with the goals of education: conduct activities and achieve results in an open controlled information space, Preparation and conduct of speeches, discussions, consultations with computer support, in including in the telecommunications environment.

Organization and conduct of group (including interschool) activities in the telecommunications environment.

Using tools for designing activities (including collective ones), visualizing roles and events.

Visual communication is the use of visual objects in the process of communication, including conceptual, organizational and other diagrams, video editing.

Prediction, design and relative assessment of individual student progress based on the current state, personality characteristics, previous history, previously accumulated statistical information about various students.

Assessment of the quality of digital educational resources (sources, tools) in relation to the specified educational tasks of their use.

Taking into account the public information space, in particular, youth.

Subject-pedagogical component After the formulation of the competence element, the subjects and groups of subjects in which this element is used are indicated in parentheses.

Setting up and conducting an experiment in virtual laboratories of your subject (natural and mathematical sciences, economics, ecology, sociology).

Obtaining an array of numerical data using automatic reading from digital

measuring devices (sensors) marking of video images, subsequent measurements and accumulation of experimental data (natural and mathematical sciences, geography).

Numerical data processing using computer statistics and visualization tools (natural and mathematical sciences, economics, ecology, sociology).

Geolocation. Entering information into geoinformation systems. Recognition of objects on maps and satellite images, combining maps and images (geography, ecology, economics, biology).

The use of digital determinants, their complement (biology).

Knowledge of high-quality information sources of your subject, including:

Literary texts and film adaptations, o historical documents, including historical maps. Representation of information in family trees and on time lines (history,

social studies). The use of digital technologies of musical composition and performance (music). The use of digital technologies of visual creativity, including animation, animation, three-dimensional graphics and prototyping (art, technology, literature). Design of virtual and real devices with digital control (technology, computer science).

Teacher support for the implementation of all elements of the subject-pedagogical component of the subject in the work of students.

Today, instead of ICT compactness, there is more and more talk about digital literacy of teaching staff. So digital literacy is a set of knowledge and skills that are necessary for the safe and effective use of digital technologies and Internet resources. The main aspects of digital literacy are:

digital consumption (active use of mobile and stationary Internet, Internet media, social networks, public services, telemedicine and cloud technologies).

digital competencies (skills and abilities to search for information, use digital devices, social network functionality, conduct financial transactions and online purchases and production of multimedia content.

Digital security (ensuring your own protection of personal data, the use of strong passwords, legal content and information storage.

The Canadian Center for Digital and Media Literacy has formulated criteria for achieving digital literacy:

media literacy: critical attitude to mass media;

information literacy: skills of finding the right information and tools to work with it, the ability to quickly master these tools;

communicative competence: communication skills with other users;

creative competence: the skills of producing information in its various forms and formats.

Characteristic "Educational concept fixes the ways of organizing educational process, typical interactions between students and teachers, which are largely predetermines the process of introducing ICT. In the traditional didactic approach, the teacher considers themselves as the main content carrier in their subject area. His job is to convey it.

Content up to pupils. Therefore, he uses ICT, first of all, for the "delivery" of educational material. On the contrary, an educational concept focused primarily on the needs of students (learner-centered philosophy), proceeds from the fact that the content of the teaching comes to them from many sources. It is clear that with this approach, ICT and digital educational resources are considered, first of all, as a tool for the educational work of schoolchildren.

The characteristic “Planning” captures the way in which general ideas about the desired future and goals in practical plans for informatization of the school in accordance with the accepted educational concept.

The characteristic “Equipment and resources” describes the conditions for the use of ICT for formation of the learning environment at school. The equipment includes such infrastructure elements such as electricity, furniture, communication channels for Internet access, etc. Insufficient ergonomic furniture, for example, can not only reduce the efficiency of ICT use, but also damage the health of students. Resources include all technological devices (system blocks, monitors, peripheral devices, etc.), as well as software, digital educational resources, audio and video recordings, various documentation (including paper handbooks, technical manuals, etc.).

The characteristic "Place in the curriculum" shows how intensively ICT is included in systematic study work. Depending on the school's approach to the process informatization (or the stage of deployment of this work), the place of ICT in the curriculum can change significantly. The characteristic “ICT training of school employees” captures the changing emphasis in the content of professional training of teachers. The spectrum of these changes includes initial acquaintance with ICT, the formation of technological literacy and pedagogical ICT competence of teachers, as well as the mastery of new pedagogical technologies that are not directly related to ICT, but have become possible in an ICT-saturated environment. educational environment

The characteristic "Public Relations" describes the involvement of the local community in the work schools. In the process of informatization of the school, this involvement changes, including qualitatively.

At the initial stages (Origin and Implementation), the connections between the school and the community are traditional: the school occasionally seeks help in buying new equipment, repairing it, etc. On subsequent stages (Diffusion and Transformation) the educational environment is increasingly going beyond

school building. The school involves in its work not only individual parents, but also all local community (enterprises, cultural and religious organizations, etc.), turning into its educational resource, to one of the centers of social life.

The characteristic "Evaluation" captures the change in the assessment of the work of the school and the assessment of achievements students. Both assessments are closely intertwined. As regards the assessment of student achievement,

In the process of school informatization, there is a change not only in tools, but also in methods measurements. So, work with a pencil and paper is replaced by work on a computer. Teachers move from ascertaining to formative assessment, from formal methods (tests success) to authentic (assessment of the results of the project work of students, the formation portfolio). The assessment given by the teacher is increasingly being replaced by self-assessment and grades given to the student by other members of the learning community.

So, in pedagogical research, the main content of the informational approach is to study and highlight the informational aspect in the framework of the educational process. In this case, the main goal of the information approach is the desire for effective use of the information field in the pedagogical system, increasing its efficiency, manageability and effectiveness. This approach assumes wide technical possibilities of using the latest technical digital devices, as well as the freedom of an elementary school student in access to information, that is, involvement in the so-called phenomenon of "collective intelligence" [4, p. 19].

The use of the information approach in the formation of media competence of primary school students in the Russian language classes helps to identify not only informational factors and conditions for the formation of media competence, but also the patterns of this process. In the course of the study, we found that the informational approach allows us to form the personality of a younger student who is able to go beyond these studied norms, while improving them, as well as establishing new ones that contribute to the dynamic development of the modern media society.

Thus, in the formation of media competence in younger students within the framework of the informational approach, the dominant is not just increasing the amount of knowledge, but also acquiring versatile experience in working with media in the process of teaching the Russian language. The expected result of the formation of media competence of younger students can be considered the mastery of the ways of using literate speech in the process of working with a variety of media, the rapid independent development of new media, and the flexibility of using the native language in various activities when using media.

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